

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

Deliverable n°:	D2.4
Deliverable name:	Dissemination and communication intermediate report
Version:	1.0
Release date:	30/05/2018
Dissemination level:	Public
Status:	Approved
Author:	UPC – Pol Olivella, Pau Lloret, SmartIO – Mari K. Buckholm, Heidi Tuiskula

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.1	17/05/2018	First draft version	Pol Olivella, Pau Lloret
0.2	25/05/2018	Inputs from T2.2	Mari K. Buckholm
0.3	28/05/2018	Merged version	Pol Olivella
0.4	01/06/2018	Inputs from T2.4	Heidi Tuiskula
0.5	06/06/2018	Merged version and final remarks before the peer-review	Pol Olivella
1.0	14/06/2018	Peer-reviewed and submitted version	Pol Olivella

Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
NTNU	Venkatachalam Lakshmanan
SIN	Joseph Negreira

Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
All partners

Table of contents

Executive summary	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Website	6
2.1 Purpose	6
2.2 Structure and content	6
2.2.1 Home	7
2.2.2 The project	8
2.2.3 Deliverables	9
2.2.4 Partners	11
2.2.5 Contact	12
2.2.6 News	13
2.3 Monitoring	14
3 Social media profiles.....	15
3.1 Statistics	16
3.1.1 Twitter	18
3.1.2 Facebook	19
3.2 Research Gate	22
4 Scientific publications	23
5 Videos and press releases.....	24
5.1 News articles	24
5.2 Video interviews	24
5.3 Content	24
5.4 Newsletters	26
5.5 Professional INVADE film	27

6	KPI	27
7	Technical Advisory Group	28
	7.1 First TAG meeting	32
8	BRIDGE and other EU activities	33
9	Other dissemination tools	36
	9.1 Project presentation	36
	9.2 Poster	36
	9.3 Flyer	38
	9.4 ZENODO repository	39
10	Annexes	40
	10.1 Project presentation captures	40

Executive summary

This document reflects the dissemination and communication actions performed during the first half of the INVADE project. It reviews the measures and actions taken during the first 18 months for spreading the project objectives and evolution. The main goals of WP2 are to disseminate and communicate the project insights, while capturing and maintaining the attention of potential stakeholders. The appropriate channels were already created during the initial months of the project, and several dissemination actions through these channels have been performed to broaden the impact of the project.

Taking into account the large influence that digital media has nowadays, a big effort has been put to build the webpage of the project and connect it to the social networks. In addition, several events have been organized and other communication channels like conferences, exhibitions or journals have been used to propagate INVADE vision, objectives and results to the relevant audience. In addition, a Technical Advisory Group (TAG) has been constituted, and some descriptive videos of the project have been released. The project has been very active in the BRIDGE group. Finally, the first INVADE large scale event is under preparation and it is scheduled for 10/10/2018 in Oslo.

Using all these tools, the INVADE's communication and dissemination tasks have achieved the following numbers:

Website	News feeds		43
Social media	Twitter	Followers	190
		Tweets	193
	Facebook	Followers	
		Public posts	81
	LinkedIn	Connections/Likes	
		posts	2
YouTube	followers		
	Videos	6	
Events	Conferences		10
	Brokerage events		3
	Trade fairs and exhibitions		2
	Workshops		3
	Meetings	Local	2
		TAG	1
Publications	Conference papers		6
	Peer reviewed Journal papers		1
	News letters		3

1 Introduction

The present report describes the work done in work package (WP) 2. The report includes the performance of the communication and dissemination tools at least up to M17.

The document is structured as follows. The sections 2, 3, 4 and 5 describe the performance of each dissemination tools till M17. Section 6 reviews the key performance indicators (KPIs) status included in the DoA and the Dissemination Plan (D2.2). Section 7 explains the TAG formation and the main outputs of the first TAG meeting. Sections 8 and 9 describe the interactions between the INVADE project and the EU commission initiatives like the BRIDGE projects cluster. Finally, Section 10 describes additional dissemination tools and the public repository used to make all possible outputs publically accessible.

2 Website

2.1 Purpose

The website is accessible through the URL www.h2020invade.eu and its purpose is to serve as the main news and information hub for the dissemination and communication activities throughout the INVADE projects lifetime of three years.

The website should present project objectives and challenges, introduce the project beneficiaries, and announce key outcomes in the form of reports, presentations, articles, films, press reports (media attention) and social media posts and tweets. The website is a key tool in order to raise a common understanding about the project and will target to reach different stakeholders of the project in an effective matter.

2.2 Structure and content

The structure of the webpage includes the following menus (the information contained in each of them is detailed in the further sections):

- Home
- The project
- Deliverables
- Partners

- Contact
- News

2.2.1 Home

The home page provides a broad overview of the project. The contents of the home page are as follows. A screenshot of the home page is shown in Figure 1:

INVADE Horizon 2020

Great things are coming

We will change the way energy is used, stored and generated

Integrated electric vehicles and batteries to empower distributed and centralised storage in distribution grids.

Renewable energies and electric vehicles (EVs) change the way we consume and produce electricity. It also changes the way those who manage and distribute it must think about the electricity system – to always provide the best possible service for the connected customers. But these things are difficult, and often take a long time.

The goal of the European-funded H2020 project INVADE is to greatly speed up this process, by showing that the technologies and solutions we have today, only must be connected in new ways to solve the challenges of tomorrow.

Great things are coming
We will change the way energy is used, stored and generated

INVADE Horizon 2020
Great things are coming

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The goal of the European-funded H2020 project INVADE is to greatly speed up this process, by showing that the technologies and solutions we have today, only must be connected in new ways to solve the challenges of tomorrow.

The project started in 2017
and lasts for 3 years

A budget of 16 million €
INVADE is one of the largest European research and innovation projects ever in the field of SmartGrid & Storage

With 12 partners
Expertise in IT, smart energy and technology.
[See our partners >](#)

INVADE newsletter
[Subscribe to the project's newsletter >](#)

News [See all](#)
Our latest from INVADE

Blockchain and energy sector
Blockchain is one of the platforms for digital finance can be used to build
(2 hours ago)

@INVADEH2020: "Blockchain is one of the leading software platform for digital financial system," say Marked, Terese Troy F
(4 hours ago)

@INVADEH2020: This storage even more!

Figure 1. Screenshot of the home page

2.2.2 The project

The project page provides more detailed information about the project such as the energy services considered and information about large scale pilots that demonstrate the concept. The contents of the home page are as follows. A screenshot of the home page is shown in the Figure 2.

The INVADE project

What is it about?

Our current electrical infrastructure face several challenges in the coming years, one being a greater share of renewable energies, another is aging infrastructure. These challenges should be resolved in a cost-efficient manner.

Renewable energies set higher demands to system resilience and flexibility, as we deal with intermittent energy resources, and it is oftentimes produced locally in the distribution grid. New system infrastructure is very expensive, urging for better use of existing infrastructure in conjunction with new inexpensive technologies.

Better energy services

INVADE seeks to solve these issues by combining already existing technologies into a new framework. At the core is a cloud-based flexibility management system integrated with electric vehicles (EVs) and batteries empowering energy storage to increase the share of renewables in the smart grid. Additionally, smart control of domestic appliances will aid in load-balancing over the course of a day.

Combining physical batteries with state of the art data technology will open new marketplaces to trade energy and energy services, which in turn will provide the end-users with better services. The electric grid manager will also benefit from this by better being able to manage their resources, and discover patterns in the power consumption, all made possible by the latest technology within big data analytics.

Large-scale pilots

The project will integrate the platform with existing infrastructure and systems at pilot sites in Bulgaria, Germany, Spain, Norway and the Netherlands, and validate it through mobile, distributed and centralized use cases in the distribution grid – in large-scale demonstrations.

Novel business models and extensive exploitation activities will be able to tread the fine line between maximizing profits for a full chain of stakeholders and optimizing social welfare, while contributing to the standardization and regulation policies for the European energy market. A meaningful integration of the transport sector is represented by both the Norwegian and the Dutch pilot – the two countries with the highest penetration of EVs worldwide.

Specific project goals

1. Design a flexibility management system using batteries that supports the distribution grid and electricity market while coping with grid limitations, uncertainty and variability with high penetration of renewable energy, electric vehicles and an increased number of diverse smart grid actors.
2. Develop a model for batteries including EVs focusing on prediction of batteries lifetime and impact factors contributing to life extension, and prepare a model for optimal sizing, positioning and scheduling of batteries in the distribution grid.
3. Deliver the Integrated INVADE Platform based on Flexibility Cloud enabling flexible management algorithms,

Figure 2 Screenshot of the project section

2.2.3 Deliverables

This section contains all project deliverables and the Figure 3 is a screenshot of this section.

Work Packages and Deliverables

You can download them as they are published

- WP1: Project Management
- WP2: Communication and Dissemination
- WP3: Exploitation
- WP4: Overall INVADE architecture
- WP5: Flexibility management system
- WP6: Energy storage technologies
- WP7: Communication platform
- WP8: Integrated INVADE platform
- WP9: Business models and energy market structures
- WP10: Pilots

Work Packages and Deliverables

You can download them as they are published

WP 1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT
D1.1 Project Management Plan – Download
D1.2 Project Periodic Report n°1
D1.3 Project Periodic Report n°2
D1.4 Project Final Report
WP 2: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION
WP 3: EXPLOITATION
WP 4: OVERALL INVADE ARCHITECTURE
WP 5: FLEXIBILITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS
WP 6: ENERGY STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES
WP 7: COMMUNICATION PLATFORM
WP 8: INTEGRATED INVADE PLATFORM
WP 9: BUSINESS MODELS AND ENERGY MARKET STRUCTURES
WP 10: PILOTS

Timeline

Follow the progress of the project

Figure 3 Screenshot of the deliverables web section

2.2.4 Partners

INVADE partner companies are described in the website

Pilot Implementation

- Estabanell Energia
- Lyse Elnett AS
- ElaadNL
- Albena JsCo
- New Energy Projects GmbH (NewEn)

Research

- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
- The Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
- VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland
- Smart Innovation Norway

Technology Providers

- eSmart Systems
- Schneider Electric Norge
- GreenFlux Assets BV

Partners
INVADE partner companies

Pilot Implementation <small>Scroll down for partners in this group</small>	Research <small>Scroll down for partners in this group</small>	Technology providers <small>Scroll down for partners in this group</small>
<p>eSmart Systems Halden, Norway</p> <p>eSmart Systems is stacked with deep market knowledge experts, with a long and strong history of developing and delivering pioneering IT-system solutions on a world-class scale to world-leading energy players...</p> <p>Visit</p>		

2.2.5 Contact

Contact

Dieter Hirdes

Head of Research & Innovation

Dieter is Head of Research & Innovation at Smart Innovation Norway and project coordinator for INVADE.

Mette M. Magnussen

Head of Communication & Visualization

Mette is Head of Communication & Visualization at Smart Innovation Norway and oversees the INVADE communication and digital media.

Mari Kristine Buckholm

Journalist / Communications Specialist

Mari is a journalist at Smart Innovation Norway and is in charge of the INVADE communication and digital media content.

Pol Olivella-Rosell

Industrial Engineer

Pol is a senior engineer at CITCEA-UPC and is responsible for the communication and dissemination of the INVADE project.

Contact

Meet our INVADE team

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Head of Research & Innovation

Dieter is Head of Research & Innovation at Smart Innovation Norway and project coordinator for INVADE.

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☎ Telephone ✉ Email

INVADE

The project - Deliverables - Partners - Contact - News

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 731148.

Get close to us by following...

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2.2.6 News

News

Our latest from INVADE

News

Our latest from INVADE

Blockchain and its application in the energy sector

By Mari Kristine Buckholm, Smart Innovation Norway (25 May 2018)

Blockchain is one of the world's leading software platforms for digital assets, and the new technology can be used to build a radically better financial system.

Read more

Secretary of State opens test lab for research on EV charging

By Eric van Kaathoven, ElaadNL (24 April 2018)

Last week, the new test site of ElaadNL was opened in Arnhem, where all different types of charging stations that are used in the Netherlands are available for tests with electric cars.

Read more

"Batteries will play a central role in accelerating renewable energy deployment"

By Mari Kristine Buckholm, Smart Innovation Norway (11 April 2018)

New battery technologies are expected to offer higher energy density, faster charging, extended lifetime, and lower cost – which will be demonstrated in the INVADE pilots.

Read more

Social media

INVADE updates

@INVADEH2020 : "Blockchain is one of the world's leading software platforms for digital assets, and the new technology can be used...
<https://t.co/84ZmaGHk6> (👍 - 4 hours ago)

@INVADEH2020 : "Blockchain is one of the world's leading software platforms for digital assets, and the new technology can be used to build a radically better financial system," says CEO of Fredrikstad Energi Marked, Terese Troy Prebensen. Read more:
(👍 - 4 hours ago)

@INVADEH2020 : (👍 - 1 week ago)

@INVADEH2020 : This is going to boost focus on storage even more!
<https://electrek.co/2018/05/14/tesla-powerpack-project-grid-balancing-europe/> (👍 - 1 week ago)

@INVADEH2020 : Role of storage is significant in future grid. Check out what we are doing with storage
@INVADEH2020 | <https://t.co/TZQuGNoult>
(👍 - 1 week ago)

@Guru_Chela : RT @Guru_Chela: In @INVADEH2020 we are doing this and much more at distribution grid level. <https://t.co/239g1HuUD> (👍 - 1 week ago)

@polivros : RT @polivros: "Connecting technology and business models" @dagfinnva from @LyseAS is presenting the implementation of @INVADEH2020 in @Est... (👍 - 1 week ago)

@polivros : RT @polivros: Working session in @CITCEA for the @INVADEH2020 project regarding the

2.3 Monitoring

Both the webpage and social media have an important role for achieving a successful communication and dissemination. The reach of all channels have been monitored, and new relevant numbers and statistics have been documented every month. This allows getting statistics of their use and will help taking decisions for reinforcing those channels that are not being so consulted and to strengthen the most successful ones.

We have used Google Analytics to monitor the webpage, and since its creation in May 2017, there has been a gradual increase in traffic; website visits and number of users. See figure below:

The following figure shows an overview of page views, sessions, users (and where the users are from) during the first half of the project:

3 Social media profiles

INVADE is available in different social networks: Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube. The key objective is to outreach citizens as well as different stakeholder groups about the INVADE platform and its potential. The social networks will also be used to collect feedback and extract information from vital stakeholders, to utilize and improve the project’s platform and its business and exploitation plan.

The accounts have slightly different purposes. The purpose and target audience of different social media channels are detailed below:

- **Twitter** is used to cover ongoing news and updates from the consortium partners, and for collecting input and information. Twitter enables the stakeholders to be involved directly with live discussions during a workshop or event. We have encouraged the consortium members to tweet about their everyday work with the project, and to tag/mention @INVADEH2020, which will retweet. The tweet frequency varies according to project activity and relevance.
- **Facebook** targets the communication towards the younger generation, such as students and various national and local associations and communities promoting a sustainable way of living. Consequently, Facebook requires an appellative and rather sophisticated visual presentation of the project information because of the overload of information and advertisement in the feeds, therefore we post more videos to reach the audience/followers. Update/post frequency varies.
- **LinkedIn** is considered a network targeting stakeholders of the European industry, initiatives and associations focusing on renewable energy storage, the smart grid, and novel ICT solutions for the energy sector. The channel has been created, but not yet used or monitored. From now on, we hope it will function as a trigger for different stakeholders (e.g. electric vehicles' owners).
- **YouTube** is used for uploading video interviews and relevant videos explaining the project. This communication channel provides a more visual understanding of the project. We publish videos whenever there are happenings worth visualizing and someone is available to make them.

3.1 Statistics

All the social networks are accessible from the webpage of the project, and all channels are monitored with the purpose of knowing how successful they are and for taking future measures to extend the communication achieved.

The list of performance indicators considered for this purpose are the total number of followers and likes on Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn, the total number of tweets/posts, the monthly post reach on Facebook, and the monthly Tweet impressions and mentions.

The figure that follows show the webpage and social media statistics obtained during the first half of the INVADE project:

Year		2017											
Month	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	
Date	19.06.2017	07.07.2017	08.08.2017	07.09.2017	16.10.2017	07.11.2017	06.12.2017	09.01.2018	06.02.2018	09.03.2018	09.04.2018	07.05.2018	
Google analytics													
Web page visits (views)		635	652	616	1011	754	903	571	1327	989	736	1063	
Number of users		154	142	132	242	150	224	187	308	330	237	284	
Top news story		Presenting Sq	Electricity for	Successful Ba	The winner t	The winner t	The winner t	The winner t	Invitation to	Invitation to	Watch video	Secretary of s	
Top story page views		75	39	45	94	44	12	14	75	110	33	45	
Facebook													
Followers	43	44	47	47	64	66	73	76	87	90	97	101	
Likes	39	40	43	43	57	60	67	70	80	83	87	91	
Posts (total)												81	
Post reach (monthly)	677	1181	950	646	2606	1101	1928	254	1258	1041	620	406	
Top post	This fast-gro	The multinat	SIN has lande	When SIN's Hi	From today's	Empower is c	Video interv	How can end	Join our work	The impact o	The INVADE	New battery	
Top post reach	134	293	327	366	881	604	1917	254	975	544	430	329	
Twitter													
Followers	77	86	99	109	134	139	152	158	165	173	174	188	
Likes	6	8	8	8	35	36	38	42	46	57	63	70	
Tweets (total)	76	86	98	104	130	140	143	148	154	173	180	190	
Tweet impressions (monthly)												4521	
Number of mentions (monthly)												23	

3.1.1 Twitter

At the moment, the Twitter account (@invadeh2020) is the most frequently used social media channel. It allows commenting and exchanging points of view around INVADE and related subjects internationally.

On June 16th 2017, we had attained 77 followers and published 76 tweets, and on May 25th 2018, we have 192 followers and 194 tweets:

For the past month, we have had 7432 tweet impressions, and 21 mentions:

3.1.2 Facebook

The Facebook activity is not as frequent as the Twitter activity. On June 16th 2017, we had attained 43 Facebook followers and published 10 posts, and on May 25th 2018, we have 105 followers and 84 posts.

The screenshot shows the Facebook page for 'Invade H2020 project' (@invadeh2020). The page header includes navigation options like 'Page', 'Inbox', 'Notifications', 'Insights', 'Publishing Tools', 'Promotions', 'Settings', and 'Help'. The profile picture features the 'INVADE' logo and the European Union flag. The main content is a post titled 'Invade H2020 project' published by Mari Kristine Buckholm 6 hours ago. The post text reads: "Blockchain is one of the world's leading software platforms for digital assets, and the new technology can be used to build a radically better financial system," says CEO of Fredrikstad Energi Marked, Terese Troy Prebensen. Read more: [link]. The post includes a photo of a woman in a green jacket standing next to a digital display. Below the photo, the text says: "Blockchain and its application in the energy sector – Invade. Blockchain technology has become known to more and more people in all corners of the world over the past few years. But, what is it exactly? H2020INVADE.EU". The post has 31 people reached and 95 likes. The right sidebar shows analytics: 46 post reach this week and 5 video views this week. The 'Community' section shows 105 people follow this page. The 'About' section identifies it as a Nonprofit Organization with a website link http://h2020invade.eu/.

For the past month, our posts have reached 352 people (which is a bit below average):

The following figures compare the two social media channels (Twitter and Facebook) in terms of followers and likes.

Table 1 Social media followers

Table 2 Social media likes

The numbers indicate that the EU Horizon 2020 project audience is more active on Twitter than Facebook.

3.2 Research Gate

Research Gate is a relevant social media for researchers. INVADE has a project profile created which collects all publications, opens debates about technical issues like battery management systems in the cloud (<https://www.researchgate.net/project/INVADE-H2020/update/5a53911ab53d2f0bba49c5cd>)

4 Scientific publications

Publications in scientific conferences and peer-reviewed journals are being published to share project's achievements with experts in the field. Indicative list of published papers in conferences and peer-reviewed journals is given on Table 3.

Table 3: Published conference and peer-reviewed papers

Title	Publication type	Conference/Journal	Deadline	Partner in charge	Collaboration
Value of prosumer house batteries: Experiences across the EU	Conference	IAEE Groningen 2018	DONE	NTNU	
Improved methods for stakeholder analysis to unveil vital roles and responsibilities in the future flexibility markets	Conference	CIREN Workshop 2018	DONE	SIN	
The INVADE project: Towards the flexibility operator concept and its application to the Spanish pilot	Conference	CIREN Workshop 2018	DONE	UPC	eSmart, Estabanell
Platform based business models in the future energy market	Conference	CIREN Workshop 2018	DONE	LYSE	SIN, Stavanger kommune
Digital ecosystems as a disruptive force of flexibility services in the energy sector	Conference	IAEE Groningen 2018	DONE	SIN	LYSE
End-user flexibility: Implications for Prosumers and Computational Challenges	Conference	CMS 2018: Conference on computational management science	DONE	NTNU	
Local Flexibility Market Design for Aggregators Providing Multiple Flexibility Services at Distribution Network Level	Peer-reviewed journal	Energies - MDPI	DONE	UPC	eSmart, SIN

5 Videos and press releases

5.1 News articles

We have published 34 news articles on the webpage since the website was up and running in May 2017. Initially, we created a communication and social media plan with the ambition of publishing 1-2 news articles on the website a week. This goal has been modified during the project lifetime, simply because the project activity varies in different time periods. As the new objective has been to publish news whenever there is something relevant happening and worth telling INVADE stakeholders, we have roughly published articles on the webpage twice a month (more often in social media).

5.2 Video interviews

The Youtube channel called INVADE H2020 project was created to upload video interviews and relevant videos explaining the project. This communication channel provides a more visual understanding of the project. Videos are always posted both on Facebook and Youtube, and then the Youtube link is posted on the webpage under News. In addition, we post all news articles published on the webpage in our social media channels. So far, five videos have been published in our Youtube channel.

5.3 Content

Monitoring the post reach and likes in social media, it has become clear that videos engage more people than simple articles. The first video interview we posted on Facebook reached a total of 1917 people, which crushed the last record of 881 people (a post about an INVADE consortium meeting in Barcelona). It has also become clear that articles, tweets and posts documenting project happenings (meetings and events) using both text and pictures engage a lot of people – because there are often many participants from different countries and partner companies.

Table 4 overview of articles and videos published in our INVADE channels

English title	Activity according to EC classification type	Authors	Date of publication	Publisher	Place of publication	Open access type	Brief description
Grand opening of test site for EV charging	Video/Film	Eric van Kaathove (ElaadNL)	04/05/18	Youtube INVADE channel	Arnhem, The Nederland's	Yes, Gold	On April 18th, Dutch State Secretary for Infrastructure and Water Management, Stientje van Veldhoven, officially opened the new Elaad test lab for research on EV charging in the business park Arnhems Buiten.
Joseph's top INVADE advice	Video/Film	Mari Buckholm (SIN)	20/03/18	Youtube INVADE channel	Halden, Norway	Yes, Gold	Joseph Negreira, International Project Manager at Smart Innovation Norway, explains which challenges the INVADE project is facing and gives his best advice to ensure a successful result.
INVADE workshop in Oslo, March 2018	Video/Film	Mari Buckholm (SIN)	12/03/18	Youtube INVADE channel	Oslo, Norway	Yes, Gold	The INVADE workshop in Oslo on March 6th offered an ample opportunity to influence the outcome of the EU project and catered for future pick-ups of concepts, software, hardware, new services, analyses and more. The goal was to harvest input that could shape the pilots and research activities. The video displays the different participants sharing their thoughts about the project so far.
Sanket Puranik talks about the importance of INVADE stakeholders	Video/Film	Mari Buckholm, Sanket Puranik (SIN)	01/03/18	Youtube INVADE channel	Halden, Norway	Yes, Gold	The EU Horizon 2020 project INVADE has just moved into its second year and partners are currently trying to reach out to harvest input that can shape the pilots and research activities. How can different players in the electricity domain best capitalize on storage and the flexibility it offers?
INVADE impact: How to make money in the new power market	Video/Film	Mari Buckholm, Håkon Duus (SIN)	18/12/17	Youtube INVADE channel	Halden, Norway	Yes, Gold	Smart Innovation Norway's Energy Systems researcher, Håkon Duus, talks about positioning technology for tomorrow's energy market.
Researchers' talk about INVADE	Video/Film	Mari Buckholm, Iliana Ilieva, Jayaprakash Rajasekharan (SIN)	16/11/17	Youtube INVADE channel	Halden, Norway	Yes, Gold	We asked Smart Innovation Norway's Iliana Ilieva and Jayaprakash Rajasekharan about their INVADE contributions, and especially; what makes the project so interesting?

5.4 Newsletters

We will also send out newsletters during the project lifetime, the first one coming up during the autumn. To reach as much people as possible, we have already created a sign-up button (see figures below) on the front page of <https://h2020invade.eu/>. So far, nine people have signed up for INVADE newsletters. They will constitute the network of interest.

INVADE Horizon 2020

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A budget of **16 million €**

INVADE is one of the largest European research and innovation projects ever in the field of SmartGrid & Storage

With **12 partners**

Expertise in IT, smart energy and technology.

[See our partners >](#)

INVADE newsletter

[Subscribe to the project's newsletter >](#)

The **five pilot sites** are located in:

Norway Germany Spain The Netherlands Bulgaria

INVADE newsletter

Welcome to the EU Horizon 2020 INVADE project newsletter!

Email Address

First Name

Last Name

Company

Subscribe to list

5.5 Professional INVADE film

During May 2018, a professional and extended branding film of the project will be made by the film production company Nordic Media Lab. This will explain the vision, scope and goal of the project. The movie is well under way and is expected to be finished in early June.

6 KPI

The status of communication and dissemination commitments that include contributions to project milestones are detailed below. This table records the commitments achieved during the project and will monitor their evolution. Those that have been achieved have their status marked in green, those that have been postponed or changed have been marked in blue and those that have not been carried out yet have been marked in grey if the reason is that they are planned as future actions and in red if they have not been done yet.

Table 5: C&D obligations

Action	Commitment	Status
Website	1 INVADE project website: www.invadeh2020.eu	Done: created
		On-going: updates
Social networks	Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter project accounts.	Done: created
		On-going: updates
Press releases	3 formal announcements. First at M3	1 done
		On-going
Project video	1 project video at M18	Done
Flyer	1 flyer	Done
Newsletters	4 newsletters. Two generic newsletters at the beginning and the end of the project, and two newsletters about pilots, after the initial phase and after the final deployment.	1 postponed
		3 pending
Local meetings	Number not specified	2 done
Technical Advisory Group	15 members maximum and 3 physical meetings	1 done
		2 pending
Project events	2 large-scale project events	1 postponed to M22
		1 pending
Workshops	8 technical workshops and 2 business workshops	5 done

		5 pending
Conference presentations	28 presentations (national + international conferences)	6 done
		22 pending
Demonstrations	Number not specified	-
Scientific Papers, Journal articles	13 scientific papers to indexed and peer-reviewed journals	1 done
		12 pending
Reports and other documents	Number not specified	4 done
Programme meetings	Number not specified	??

In a similar way, the status of the committed project workshops is detailed in Table 6. Changes from D2.2 are marked in blue.

Table 6: Workshop commitments

Workshop description	Resp.	Place	Date	WP	Status
INVADE concept and overall architecture model	UPC	Barcelona	M6 M3	WP4	Done
INVADE architecture developed, focused on pilot implementation	UPC	Barcelona	M4 M5	WP4	Done
Grid integration of battery storages, with emphasis on benefits for distribution grid companies	VTT	Espoo	M14 M15	WP6	Done
Market projections, cost-benefit analyses, SWOT analyses and to establish closer interactions with relevant stakeholders	SmartIO	Oslo	M14	WP3	Done
Grid integration of energy storage, with emphasis on potential value creation.	NTNU	Trondheim	M17	WP5	On-going

7 Technical Advisory Group

The Technical Advisory Group (TAG) is designed to gain additional technical expertise on R&D effort and demonstrations and have a more focused strategic vision. It will include members from the most important types of stakeholders and high-level scientific researchers.

The creation of the TAG was one of the objectives of the first months of the project. For this purpose, a letter of invitation and a FAQ (Frequently Asked Questions) document were prepared to be sent to potential TAG candidates (Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively). The choice of the TAG candidates was a consensus among project partners.

Figure 4: Letter of invitation for TAG candidates

Figure 5: Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) for TAG members

The TAG core and satellite members are detailed at Table 7.

TAG member expertise

Figure 6 Technical advisory group members' expertise

Full name	Expertise	Academy / Company	Institution/Company	Country	Relation proposed
Eloy Alvarez	Energy Policy & Regulation	A	Spanish Royal Academy of Engineering	Spain	Core
Mark Akehurst	Energy retail business	C	ENGIE	France	Core
Michael John	Privacy and Security	C	ENCS	The Netherlands	Core
Valeriy Vyatkin	Internet of Energy	A	Aalto University	Finland	Core
David Robinson	Energy policy & Regulation	A	The Oxford Institute for Energy Studies	UK	Core
Josef Noll	Cybersecurity	A	University of Oslo	Norway	Satellite
Madeleine Gibescu	Flexibility markets	A	TU Eindhoven	The Netherlands	Satellite
Pierre Pinson	Flexibility markets	A	DTU	Denmark	Satellite
José Carlos Fernández Pérez	Energy Policy & Regulation	C	Spanish TSO Red eléctrica de España	Spain	Satellite
Magnus Linden	Energy Policy & Regulation	C	Sweco	Sweden	Satellite
Salvador Baille	Business developments	C	Intelis	Norway	Satellite
Miguel Pardo	DSO	C	Spanish DSO Endesa	Spain	Satellite
Ernesto Damiani	Internet of Energy	A	CINI (Consorzio Interuniversitario Nazionale per l'Informatica)	Italy	Satellite
Dimitrios Zafirakis	RES integration, Energy storage	A	Technological Educational Institute of Piraeus	Greece	Satellite
Monique Voogt	Energy Policy & Regulation	C	SQC	Belgium	Satellite
Sergio Ugarte	Energy Policy & Regulation	C	SQC	Spain	Satellite
Theresa Eich	Energy Policy & Regulation	C	Frontier economics	Spain	Satellite
Jaume Gratacós	Energy policy & regulation, energy retail business	C	ICAEN Regional energy agency	Spain	Satellite
Víctor Bermúdez Llamusí	TSO and demand side management	C	Spanish TSO Red eléctrica de España	Spain	Satellite
Jaume Caus	DSO	C	Spanish DSO Endesa	Spain	Satellite
Daniel Davi	Energy policy & Regulation	C&A	The chair of energy sustainability at the UB & Endesa (Spanish DSO)	Spain	Satellite
Josep Ballart	Energy policy & Regulation	C	Industrial Engineers Association of Catalonia	Spain	Satellite

Table 7: TAG members

7.1 First TAG meeting

The first TAG meeting was held in Barcelona on 13th June 2017. The objective was to present the INVADE concept design and receive feedback from the TAG members.

The meeting agenda was:

Tuesday 13th June 2017. Concept design description + TAG meeting

09:00	Welcome by representatives from CITCEA-UPC
09:30	TAG description and objectives (UPC)
09:45	TAG member's presentation
10:00	Concept design (WP4 – UPC) + discussion
11:15	Coffee break*
11:30	Concept design (WP4 – UPC) + discussion
12:45	Lunch*
14:00	Review of flexibility business models (WP9 – Lyse) + discussion
15:00	Pilots review: description and special necessities (WP10: Schneider and pilot responsible partners) + discussion
16:15	Coffee break*
16:30	Pilots review: description and special necessities (WP10: Schneider and pilot responsible partners) + discussion
17:30	TAG members' final recommendations for INVADE
18:00	Review of agreements
20:30	Dinner, restaurant TBD*

* Courtesy of CITCEA-UPC

Meeting attendees were:

Project members		TAG members	
SmartIO	Håkon Duus	Spanish Royal Academy of Engineering	Eloy Alvarez
	Christian Kunze	ENCS	Michael John
UPC	Roberto Villafafila	SQC	Sergio Ugarte
	Andreas Sumper	Endesa (Spanish DSO)	Jaume Caus Caldere
	Pol Olivella		Miguel Pardo
	Pau Lloret	ICAEN (Catalan Energy Agency)	Jaume Gratacós
	Íngrid Munné Collados	Frontier economics	Theresa Eich
NTNU	Magnus Korpås	UPC Master student	Damiano Fraizzoli
VTT	Ari Hentunen	Chair of energy sustainability & Endesa (Spanish DSO)	Daniel Daví

eSmart	Stig Ødegaard Ottesen	REE (Spanish TSO)	Víctor Bermudez
NewEn	Arne Henn	COEIC (Industrial Engineers Association of Catalonia)	Josep Ballart
Albena	Dimitar Stanev		
	Irena Hristova		
Schneider	Per Gjerløw		
	Cristóbal Cordobés		
	Svein Lien		
	Abdul Wahab		
Lyse	Sindre Tøsse		
EPESA	Ramón Gallart		
	Farah Cheaib		
Elaad	Arjan Wargers		
	Patrick Rademakers		
GreenFlux	Michel Bayings		

8 BRIDGE and other EU activities

INVADE Project has been actively contributing into the BRIDGE community. Project has assigned representatives for each working group, which are shown in the table below:

Consortium considers the collaboration fruitful for the dissemination of the INVADE learnings and also sees working groups as excellent platforms for learning from other H2020 projects and finding collaboration possibilities.

INVADE participation in BRIDGE Coordination working group is shown in the table below:

Date	Location	What event/activity was attended?	Who attended?	Main issues addressed?	INVADE contribution in the event	INVADE ToDo list for future and responsible person
18-19/01/2018	Brussels	INEA 4th BRIDGE meeting – project coordinators' meeting	Dieter Hirdes			

INVADE participation in BRIDGE Customer Engagement working group is shown in the table below:

Date	Location	What event/activity was attended?	Who attended?	Main issues addressed?	INVADE contribution in the event	INVADE ToDo list for future and responsible person
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20-21/11/17	Bru ssel s	CE General meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2017	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.
22/11/2017	Bru ssel s	BRIDGE Gen- eral meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2017	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.
07/12/2017	Sky pe	CE General meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2017	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.
14/12/2017	Sky pe	CE General meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2017	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.
21/12/2017	Sky pe	CE General meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2017	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.
11/01/2018	Sky pe	CE General meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2017	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.
01/03/2018	Sky pe	CE General meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2018	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.
13/04/2018	Sky pe	CE General meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2018	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.
18/05/2018	Sky pe	CE General meeting	Joseph Negreira	Work on Delivera- ble 2015-2018	Leader of sub-group A	Generate contributions to the deliverable.

INVADE participation in BRIDGE Data Management working group is shown in the table below:

Date	Lo- ca- tion	What event/activ- ity was at- tended?	Who attended?	Main is- sues ad- dressed?	INVADE contribution in the event	INVADE ToDo list for future and responsible person
24/05/18	Re- mot e	Completed Data han- dling ques- tionnaire	The template was completed by Mark Fisher and Terje Lundby	Data ac- cess and interoper- ability	The questionnaire was filled out based on data access and interoperabil- ity in the Norwegian IN- VADE pilot.	No specific tasks at the moment

INVADE participation in BRIDGE Energy Regulation working group is shown in the table below:

Date	Location	What event/activity was attended?	Who attended?	Main issues addressed?	INVADE contribution in the event	INVADE ToDo list for future and responsible person
03/04/2017	Remotely	Support requested by Bridge managers	Andreas Sumper & Pol Olivella	STEP 2 - Analysis of the Clean Energy Package	Clean energy package reading	Send major issues
26/04/2017	Remotely	Support requested by Bridge managers	Pol Olivella	STEP 2 - Analysis of the Clean Energy Package	Clean energy package reading	Send major issues
01/06/2017	Remotely	Support requested by Bridge managers	Andreas Sumper & Pol Olivella	STEP 3 - Analysis of the Clean Energy Package	4 articles reviewed	Send articles reviewed
20/11/2017	Brussels	Bridge regulation WG meeting	Pol Olivella	Presentation of the "Feedback on the Clean Energy Package proposals" report + Interactive session on the year's activities and EC's expectations	Project presentation + Lead of one sub-issue regarding storage	Send sub-issue reviewed and coordination of the sub-group
12/02/2018	Remotely	Storage issues sub-working group	Pol Olivella	Battery flexibility services	Definition of regulatory barriers	Provide inputs to the bridge report of 2018
02/03/2018	Remotely	Storage issues sub-working group	Pol Olivella	Battery flexibility services	Definition of regulatory barriers	Create a questionnaire for other H2020 projects collaborating in the Bridge cluster
20/04/2018	Remotely	Storage questionnaire	Pol Olivella	Battery flexibility services	Creation of the H2020 questionnaire	Analyse the replies from the questionnaire
31/05/2018	Remotely	Storage regulation recommendations	Pol Olivella	Battery flexibility services	Draft of regulatory recommendations	Send draft regulatory recommendations to Dowel for the new Bridge report

9 Other dissemination tools

9.1 Project presentation

In order to help to disseminate the project while reaching possible potential stakeholders in events like congress, conferences, exhibitions or workshops, a presentation describing the objectives and the consortium has been prepared (see captions in Annex 10.1).

9.2 Poster

To be shown to delegates in conferences, events or workshops, a poster of the project was created (see flyer in Figure 7).

Figure 7: Poster of the INVADE project

9.3 Flyer

A flyer presenting key insights about the project was created to be handed out at conferences, to colleagues and to engaged or interested stakeholders (see flyer in Figure 8).

INVADE

Integrated electric vehicles and batteries to empower distributed and centralised storage in distribution grids

www.h2020invade.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 731148.

WHAT IS IT ABOUT?

Our current electrical infrastructure faces several challenges in the coming years, one being a greater share of renewable energies, another is aging infrastructure. These challenges should be resolved in a cost-efficient manner.

Renewable energies set higher demands to system resilience and flexibility, as we deal with intermittent energy resources, and are often produced locally in the distribution grid. New system infrastructure is very expensive, urging for better use of existing infrastructure in conjunction with new inexpensive technologies.

INVADE seeks to solve these issues by combining already existing technologies into a new framework. At the core is a cloud-based flexibility management system integrated with electric vehicles (EVs) and batteries empowering energy storage to increase the share of renewables in the smart grid. Additionally, smart control of domestic appliances will aid in load-balancing over the course of a day.

Combining physical batteries with state of the art data technology will open new marketplaces to trade energy and energy services, which in turn will provide the latest technology within big data analytics.

12 PARTNERS
With expertise in IT, smart energy and technology

16 MILLION EUROS
INVADE is a large European research and innovation project in the field of SmartGrid & Storage

5 PILOT SITES
Located in Germany, Norway, Spain, Bulgaria and The Netherlands

Want to know more, visit us at www.h2020invade.eu

Figure 8: Flyer of the INVADE project

9.4 ZENODO repository

A community is created into the ZENODO public repository to add uploads from the project and deposit research data. Since now, 14 deliverables, the project presentation and a journal paper were published in this repository. INVADE community in ZENODO can be found following this link:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/invade/?page=1&size=20>

The screenshot shows the ZENODO repository interface for the INVADE H2020 Project community. The header includes the ZENODO logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. The user profile 'pol.olivella@citcea.upc.edu' is visible in the top right.

The main content area is titled 'INVADE H2020 Project' and features a 'Recent uploads' section. A search bar is provided for finding uploads within the community. Three uploads are listed:

- April 2, 2018 (1.0)** | Journal article | Open Access | View
 - Local Flexibility Market Design for Aggregators Providing Multiple Flexibility Services at Distribution Network Level**
 - Authors: Olivella-Rosell, Pol; Lloret-Gallego, Pau; Munné-Collado, Ingrid; Villafafila-Robles, Roberto; Sumper, Andreas; Ottesen, Stig Ødegaard; Rajasekharan, Jayaprakash; Bremdal, Bernt A.;
 - Description: This paper presents a general description of local flexibility markets as a market-based management mechanism for aggregators. The high penetration of distributed energy resources introduces new flexibility services like prosumer or community self-balancing, congestion management and time-of-use opt
 - Uploaded on May 23, 2018
- May 16, 2018 (1.0)** | Presentation | Open Access | View
 - INVADE project presentation**
 - Author: Olivella-Rosell, Pol; Lloret-Gallego, Pau; Thomsen, Ketil;
 - Description: INVADE project concept presentation
 - Uploaded on May 23, 2018
- December 20, 2017 (1.0)** | Project deliverable | Open Access | View
 - Simplified Battery operation and control algorithm**
 - Authors: Ottesen, Stig Ødegaard; Olivella-Rosell, Pol; Lloret-Gallego, Pau; Hentunen, Ari; Crespo del Granado, Pedro; Bjarghov, Sigurd; Lakshmanan, Venkatachalam; Aghaei, Jamshid;
 - Description: The main objective of the INVADE project is to study possibilities to increase RES penetration and integration in the power system by adding more storage, i.e., batteries. The analysis centres on the flexibility services that different types of storages can provide, namely: centralized, distributed
 - Uploaded on May 10, 2018

On the right side, there is a 'New upload' button and a section titled 'Want your upload to appear in this community?' with the following instructions:

- Click the button above to upload straight to this community.
- The community curator is notified, and will either accept or reject your upload (see community curation policy above).
- If your upload is rejected by the curator, it will still be available on Zenodo, just not in this community.

Below this is the 'Community' section, which features the INVADE logo and the following description:

INVADE H2020 Project
This community will discuss and share about flexibility in distribution networks in smart grid dominated environments. Specially flexibility provided by electric vehicles and small/mid-size batteries

10 Annexes

10.1 Project presentation captures

INTEGRATED ELECTRIC VEHICLES AND BATTERIES TO EMPOWER DISTRIBUTED AND CENTRALISED STORAGE IN DISTRIBUTION GRIDS

INVADE

WHAT ARE WE AIMING AT?

Our current electric infrastructure face several challenges in the coming years, and being in a **greater state of renewable energies** involves **renewing infrastructure**. These challenges should be resolved in a **cost-efficient manner**.

WHAT ARE WE AIMING AT?

The INVADE project aims to provide a **Cloud-based flexibility management system** integrated with EVs and batteries, optimising energy storage at mobile, distributed and centralised levels to increase renewable share in the local distribution grid.

RENEWABLE GENERATION AND EVs ARE COMING

Renewable power forecast to grow by 36% over 2015-21, making it the fastest growing source of electricity generation. Source: IEA

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The system is a peer-to-peer system based on direct control of demand and supply. The flexibility operator (FO) takes decisions based on flexibility contracts. Three early patterns can be integrated:

- Energy storage
- EVs
- Renewable energy

Flexibility resources to be controlled are:

- Batteries
- Electric vehicles
- Photovoltaic panels
- Water heaters
- Heat pumps

Flexibility services for:

- Grid users/prosumers reducing the electricity bill
- BRP to reduce imbalance penalties
- DSO to control grid congestions

INVADE will be **able** to provide flexibility to prosumers, DSOs and BRPs in the following cases:

FLEXIBILITY SERVICES

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services (INVADE)	Descriptive Flexibility usage
DSO	Congestion management	Avoiding the thermal overload of active components by reducing power flows when below their maximum capacity
	Voltage reactive power control	Using local flexibility by increasing the load or decreasing generation in an effort to avoid exceeding the voltage limit. Voltage control is typically installed when solar PV systems generate significant unbalanced electricity
BRP	Controlled curtailment	Preventing supply imbalance in a given grid section when a load occurs in a section of the grid feeding into it
	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	During each day, a rigorous flow control is implemented to ensure that the day-ahead market clearing is met. It enables the BRP to identify and control its generation portfolio
Prosumer	Self-heating/cooling	Reducing imbalance in the BRP market by curtailment to avoid imbalance charges. The BRP control system bid on the imbalance market with their flexibility to avoid imbalances
	Renewable energy	Facilitate high renewable curtailment to increase renewable energy generation and avoid imbalance charges
Prosumer	Virtual power plant	Resolving the maximum cost goal sharing that the Prosumer consumes when a predefined condition is met, such as other production, storage or charging
	Renewable energy	Using local flexibility by increasing the load or decreasing generation in an effort to avoid exceeding the voltage limit. Voltage control is typically installed when solar PV systems generate significant unbalanced electricity

USE CASES

Use cases (UC):

- Mobile energy storage using EVs for V2G, V2B and V2H operations
- Centralised energy storage using an array of batteries at the substation or street level
- Distributed energy storage using in-house batteries at the household level
- Hybrid level energy storage and power addressing a combination of use cases 2 and 3

PILOTS IMPLEMENTATIONS

5 Pilots:

- Norway: UC 1, 3, 4
- The Netherlands: UC 1
- Bulgaria: UC 2
- Spain: UC 2
- Germany: UC 4

